

Feasibility of electrical bio-impedance sensing for tissue discrimination to assist deep needle insertion

Yao Zhang¹, Zhuoqi Cheng², Mouloud Ourak¹,

Thiusius Rajeeth Savarimuthu², and Emmanuel Vander Poorten¹
¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, KU Leuven, Belgium*

²*The Maersk Mc-Kinney Møller Institute, University of Southern Denmark, Denmark*
yao.zhang@kuleuven.be

INTRODUCTION

Sensor-embedded smart needle insertion is critical for minimizing risks for many medical procedures such as deep femoral artery insertion [1]. Improved tissue discrimination can significantly enhance precision and safety during interventions. While ultrasound (US) and fluoroscopy are commonly used for real-time guidance, they require significant training, and present challenges in emergency settings due to their bulky equipment and, in the case of fluoroscopy, radiation exposure [2].

Electrical bio-impedance (EBI) presents a promising alternative with advantages such as low cost, non-radiative operation, and effective proximity sensing [3]. By analyzing the electrical field at the needle electrode, EBI assesses tissue conductivity, which is influenced by complex cellular and molecular structures, enabling detailed tissue characterization. However, previous approaches relied on measured amplitude or phase values to differentiate tissues [4]. For ease of use, it would be beneficial to develop algorithms that are independent of the needle's specific shape and size. To address this, we propose a model that converts EBI into tissue-specific electrical conductivity, providing a universal and reliable reference for tissue characterization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To improve the success rate of femoral artery access, this work introduces a tripolar electrode configuration with a needle-tip electrode and two surface electrodes. This enables conductivity measurements at different depths to enhance tissue characterization, reducing procedural risks. The feasibility of using EBI for tissue discrimination was evaluated through simulations conducted on MATLAB's Electrical Impedance Tomography and Diffuse Optical Tomography Reconstruction Software (EIDORS) platform, which employs the finite element method (FEM) to mesh a 200×200×150 mm tissue block, assign electrical conductivity values (1 S/m), and compute potential distributions of each meshing. A $\phi 1$ mm diameter needle (CSE, A) injected current at depths of

1–30 mm insertion, while two $\phi 1$ mm surface electrodes (M and N) served as voltage measurement electrodes (VME), as shown in Fig. 1(a). M was 20 mm from the needle insertion point, and N was 40 mm away, with a 20 mm gap between M and N . Figure 1(a) shows the electrodes marked in green. The impedance of M and N was calculated from the simulation and served as the ground truth.

Fig. 1 (a) EIDORS modeling; (b) Compare the estimated conductivity of needle contacting tissue and the ground truth.

The measured voltage at electrode M introduced by the current from needle tip A includes: direct flow along AM and reflected current at the tissue (σ)-air (σ_{air}) interface [5]. The needle tip A is modeled as an equivalent sphere with radius r_0 , representing the effective injection area for current distribution. Based on Maxwell's equations, the impedance at M and N is expressed in equations (1) and (2), with the reflection coefficient k in equation (3).

$$z_M = - \int_{r_0}^{|AM|} \frac{(k+1)}{4\pi\sigma r^2} dr = \frac{k+1}{4\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} - \frac{1}{r_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$z_N = - \int_{r_0}^{|AN|} \frac{(k+1)}{4\pi\sigma r^2} dr = \frac{k+1}{4\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AN|} - \frac{1}{r_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

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Fig. 2 (a) ①–electrical bio-impedance spectroscopy device; ②–motor controller; ③–motor power supply; ④–two VMEs; ⑤–multi-DOF stage; ⑥–DC motor; ⑦–IV catheter; ⑧–water tank; ⑨–cRIO; (b) experimental results of σ estimation for 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3% NaCl solutions during needle insertion.

$$k = \frac{\sigma - \sigma_{air}}{\sigma + \sigma_{air}} \quad (3)$$

Using the impedance values from the two VMEs and distances $|AM|$ and $|AN|$, the tissue's electrical conductivity σ at A can be derived as (4).

$$\sigma = \frac{k+1}{4\pi z_{MN}} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} - \frac{1}{|AN|} \right) \quad (4)$$

To validate the proposed model (4), the impedance values z_M and z_N obtained from EIDORS simulations are used to calculate the impedance z_{MN} ($z_M - z_N$) and compared to measurements from simulation.

Figure 2(a) illustrates the experimental setup, which is based on a water tank. A linear motor controls the needle (18-gauge IV catheter (BD®, USA)) insertion, while two jumper wire pins function as VMEs. All electrodes are connected to an EBI sensor (Eliko Tehnoloogia Arenduskeskus, Estonia). To simulate varying tissue conditions, the water tank was filled with saline solutions of different concentrations throughout the experiment.

RESULTS

The proposed model was initially validated in the EIDORS simulation. As shown in Fig. 1(b), the needle was simulated to insert into the block. The model's estimated conductivity (σ) is plotted in blue, while the EIDORS simulation's predefined conductivity of 1 S/m is indicated by the red dashed line. Since air is nearly non-conductive, σ_{air} is close to zero, and the reflection coefficient k is equal to 1. The results demonstrate a strong alignment between the estimated and ground truth values. To quantitatively assess the model's accuracy, the mean absolute error percentage (MAEP) was calculated using (5), where \hat{y}_i is the estimated value, y_i is the ground truth and n is the number of data points, yielding a low error of 0.57%, indicating high accuracy.

$$MAEP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{\hat{y}_i - y_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100 \quad (5)$$

The proposed model was further validated through experiments using saline solutions with three concentrations: 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3%. In the setup, the two VMEs were positioned 10 mm apart, with electrode M placed 12 mm from the needle tip insertion point. The distances $|AM|$

TABLE I Mean percentage error and standard deviation (STD) for 5 repeated trials.

Medium	Trial	1	2	3	4	5	Deviation	
							MAEP	STD
0.1% NaCl		2.61%	5.79%	5.31%	5.91%	5.91%	5.11%	1.27%
0.2% NaCl		5.32%	5.18%	5.42%	5.43%	5.00%	5.27%	0.16%
0.3% NaCl		5.04%	3.60%	3.81%	6.04%	4.14%	4.55%	0.94%

and $|AN|$ were determined based on the needle insertion depth. Using the measured EBI for each concentration, the estimated σ values are presented in Fig. 2(b), where 0.1% (red), 0.2% (blue), and 0.3% (green) results are compared against their respective reference values (dashed lines) [6]. Each experiment was repeated five times, and the MAEP results in Table I indicate that all errors remain below 6% with minimal STD, demonstrating the model's high accuracy and robustness.

DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed model in both simulations and saline experiments, highlighting its potential for tissue characterization. The small observed error is primarily due to slight discrepancies between the ideal and actual electrode dimensions but has minimal impact on the overall accuracy. By eliminating dependence on electrode size, the model ensures that EBI measurements accurately reflect the tissue's inherent conductivity, reducing variability caused by electrode dimensions. Future work will focus on *ex vivo* and *in vivo* experiments to further validate its applicability in femoral artery procedures.

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